

E-ISSN: 3115-5774

VOLUME 3 NO.2; APRIL, 2026

AUDIT COMMITTEE INDEPENDENCE AND SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING OF LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA: MODERATED BY WOMEN CHAIRPERSON

¹EMMANUEL BABATUNDE OYEDELE, SAMUEL ENIOLA AGBI, SAMUEL GAMBO JOSHUA AND SULEIMAN TAUHID

Department of Accounting,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna

¹**Corresponding Author** emmanueloyedele2887@gmail.com

doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.19831497

ABSTRACT

Sustainability reporting has gained global importance as stakeholders increasingly demand transparency on environmental, social, and governance issues. In Nigeria, Deposit Money Banks play a crucial role in advancing sustainable finance, yet their sustainability disclosures remain inconsistent and limited in scope. This study examines audit committee independence and sustainability reporting of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, while assessing the moderating role of audit committee women chairperson. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design using secondary data obtained from the annual reports of fourteen (14) listed DMBs in Nigeria covering the period 2010–2024. Multiple regression analysis was conducted using STATA software to test the study's hypotheses. The results revealed that audit committee independence had a positive and significant effect on sustainability reporting, indicating that banks with more independent audit committees are more likely to disclose transparent sustainability information. Similarly, the presence of a woman as audit committee chairperson significantly enhanced sustainability reporting quality. However, the moderating role of audit committee women chairperson in the effect of audit committee independence on sustainability reporting was found to be statistically insignificant. The study concludes that audit committee independence enhances the oversight of sustainability practices, while

the role of women as chairpersons does not enhance the effectiveness of sustainability reporting in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study thus recommends that deposit money banks in Nigeria should strengthen the independence of their audit committees and enhance female representation in leadership positions. However, since the moderating role of female chairpersons was found to be statistically insignificant, the study recommends that regulatory authorities should develop policies that go beyond mere representation and focus on empowering female leaders through targeted capacity-building programs, sustainability training, and inclusion in strategic decision-making processes.

KEYWORDS: Audit Committee Independence, Audit Committee Women Chairperson, Sustainability Reporting, Bank Size, Deposit Money Banks, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability reporting has emerged as a critical element of corporate governance, especially in the financial sector, where stakeholders demand transparency on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues. The practice of sustainability reporting has evolved significantly over the last few decades, driven by various forces including stakeholder expectations, global regulatory frameworks, and a growing awareness of corporate responsibility (Gupta & Sharma 2020). Traditionally, sustainability reporting focused primarily on environmental issues, but today, it encompasses a broad range of topics, including corporate social responsibility (CSR), governance, stakeholder engagement, and long-term value creation as indicated by KPMG, (2020). This shift reflects a growing recognition that businesses must go beyond financial performance and address the broader impact of their activities on society and the environment (Eccles & Krzus, 2018).

In Nigeria, Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) are key players in the nation's economic development, providing financial intermediation and supporting sustainability-linked financing. As global sustainability reporting frameworks such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) gain traction, Nigerian banks are increasingly expected to disclose non-financial performance indicators alongside traditional financial information (Usman, 2024; Jibril et al., 2024). Despite these expectations, the level of sustainability disclosure among Nigerian banks remains inconsistent, raising concerns about the effectiveness of governance mechanisms driving such practices.

Audit committees are central to corporate governance systems. They provide oversight on financial reporting, risk management, and internal controls, thereby promoting accountability and transparency (Buallay & Al-Ajmi, 2020). Audit committee independence, in particular, ensures objectivity in oversight and mitigates management bias in disclosure decisions. An independent audit committee enhances stakeholder trust by ensuring that sustainability disclosures are reliable, comprehensive, and aligned with global standards (Florea & Burrcă, 2024). Audit committee independence is crucial for ensuring the objectivity and effectiveness of the committee's oversight functions. Independent audit committee members are typically free from conflicts of interest, allowing them to make impartial decisions regarding the integrity of financial and sustainability reporting (Carcello et al., 2002). Independence is particularly important in the context of sustainability reporting, as it ensures that the committee is not unduly influenced by management or other internal stakeholders when reviewing ESG disclosures as opined by Fama & Jensen, (1983). However, the effectiveness of independent audit committees in influencing sustainability reporting in developing economies such as Nigeria remains underexplored.

The role of women in leadership positions has become a subject of increasing interest in the corporate governance literature. One area that has received significant attention is the influence of female directors, particularly those serving as chairpersons of audit committees, on corporate governance outcomes. Recent corporate governance research emphasizes the role of diversity in strengthening audit committee effectiveness. According to Abbasi et al., (2024), a woman chairperson on the audit committee, for instance, introduces unique leadership perspectives, ethical sensitivity, and inclusiveness that could enhance sustainability-oriented decisions. Ben Amar et al., (2024) further opined that female leadership has been linked to improved transparency and stronger ESG governance due to higher social responsibility orientation and stakeholder awareness. Thus, examining whether the presence of a woman chairperson strengthens the impact of audit committee independence on sustainability reporting is both timely and policy-relevant. The persistent gap between corporate sustainability commitments and actual disclosure practices in Nigeria's banking industry has been a major concern in identifying where the problem of this study lies (Amin et al., 2021).

In Nigeria, though Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) play a crucial role in advancing sustainable finance, their sustainability disclosures remain inconsistent and limited in scope. Despite the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) efforts through the Nigerian Sustainable Banking Principles (NSBP), several DMBs provide limited or selective ESG information (Abbasi et al., 2024). Many of these banks have audit committees dominated by executive or affiliated directors, potentially undermining independence (Tumwebaze & Kaawaase, 2022). Furthermore, gender imbalance within audit leadership structures may limit diverse oversight needed for comprehensive sustainability reporting (Gatimbu et al., 2025). This raises critical questions about whether independence and women leadership jointly enhance sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Audit committees play a pivotal role in addressing these issues by overseeing and ensuring the credibility of both financial and non-financial disclosures, including sustainability reports (Oyerogba & Oladele, 2024). However, Soyemi et al., (2024) indicated that recent empirical evidence on how certain audit committee characteristics such as its independence affect the quality of sustainability reporting in Nigerian banks are limited. This lack of insight raises questions about the role and effectiveness of audit committees in ensuring that banks meet the growing expectations for transparent and comprehensive sustainability disclosures (Alalade & Ogboi, 2024). Moreover, the increasing focus on gender diversity within corporate governance, particularly the presence of women in leadership roles, has introduced an additional layer of complexity. The role of a female audit committee chairperson a relatively understudied phenomenon in Nigerian banking may have a moderating influence on the effectiveness of audit committees.

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of audit committee independence on sustainability reporting, moderated by audit committee women chairperson of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria while the specific objectives include to;

- i. Investigate the effect of audit committee independence on sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- ii. Analyse the effect of audit committee women chairperson on sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

- iii. Assess the effect of the moderating role of audit committee women chairperson on audit committee independence and sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The following hypotheses were tested in null form;

H₀₁: Audit committee independence has no significant effect on sustainability reporting disclosure of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Audit committee women chairperson has no significant effect on sustainability reporting disclosure of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Audit committee women chairperson does not significantly moderate audit committee independence and sustainability reporting disclosure of deposit money banks in Nigeria

The study is significant as it bridges theoretical and empirical gaps in understanding governance mechanisms affecting sustainability disclosures in Nigeria's banking sector. It contributes to academic literature by extending the agency theory to gendered governance dynamics and provides policy recommendations for regulators and board nomination committees. Practically, the findings will guide financial institutions in designing more effective and inclusive audit committees that drive sustainability reporting in line with global best practices.

The scope of the study covers listed deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period 2010–2024. This 15-year period was chosen for its relevance in understanding key transformations that have shaped the Nigerian banking industry in terms of governance reforms, sustainability reporting, and the role of gender diversity in leadership positions within corporate structures. The study focuses on audit committee independence and sustainability reporting, with audit committee women chairperson as a moderating variable. Control variables such as bank size are incorporated to account for institutional differences among the sampled banks.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Sustainability reporting refers to the process of disclosing non-financial information that reflects a company's environmental, social, and governance performance. According to the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI, 2020), sustainability reporting involves communicating the organization's impact on the economy, environment, and society. Similarly, Lozano (2021) defined it as the systematic reporting of sustainability performance aimed at enhancing accountability and transparency to stakeholders. However, these definitions often emphasize external communication without detailing the governance structures driving sustainability practices. In this study, sustainability reporting is conceptualized as a structured process of disclosing ESG-related performance guided by governance oversight, particularly through independent audit committees.

The audit committee is a subcommittee of the board of directors responsible for overseeing financial reporting, risk management, and compliance processes. As noted by Aprianti et al. (2021), the audit committee serves as a vital link between management and external auditors, ensuring the integrity of corporate reports. Amin et al. (2021) further described it as an internal governance mechanism that enhances accountability and transparency by supervising disclosure processes. Despite these roles, previous definitions often neglect the evolving role of audit committees in non-financial reporting oversight. For this study, the audit committee is defined as a board subcommittee tasked with ensuring the accuracy, integrity, and completeness of both financial and sustainability disclosures.

Audit committee independence refers to the degree to which audit committee members are free from management influence and conflicts of interest. According to Buallay and Al-Ajmi (2020), independence enhances objective oversight, reduces bias, and strengthens transparency in corporate disclosures. Florea and Burcă (2024) emphasized that independent committees improve the reliability of ESG reports by ensuring that sustainability data are accurate and verifiable. However, some studies (Ademola et al., 2022) argue that mere independence without expertise may not guarantee quality oversight. In this study, audit committee independence is defined as the extent to which non-executive and unaffiliated directors exercise autonomous judgment in ensuring transparent and reliable sustainability reporting.

Gender diversity in audit committee leadership plays a vital role in shaping governance outcomes. Abbasi et al. (2024) found that female-led audit committees enhance carbon disclosure quality through ethical oversight and inclusiveness. Similarly, Ben Amar et al. (2024) observed that audit committees chaired by women reduce earnings management, indirectly strengthening sustainability accountability. However, prior studies have often limited gender considerations to mere representation rather than leadership influence. Thus, this study defines the audit committee women chairperson as a female-led audit committee head who drives governance oversight and accountability, potentially moderating the link between audit committee independence and sustainability reporting.

Bank size is a crucial control variable in corporate disclosure studies. Larger banks are more visible to stakeholders and subject to greater regulatory scrutiny, motivating them to provide more detailed sustainability disclosures (Usman, 2024). Smaller banks, on the other hand, may face resource constraints that limit the depth of their sustainability reporting. Controlling for bank size allows the study to isolate the true effects of audit committee independence and gender leadership on sustainability reporting performance.

While multiple theories such as Gender Diversity Theory (Terjesen et al., 2009) and Resource Dependency Theory (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978) are relevant, this study is anchored on Agency Theory. This theory posits that audit committees serve as monitoring mechanisms to align management's actions with shareholders' interests (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Independent audit committees minimize information asymmetry and ensure credible reporting. Integrating gender diversity aligns with stakeholder theory principles, as female leadership tends to represent broader stakeholder perspectives, emphasizing ethical accountability and social responsibility (Freeman, 1984). Thus, the combination of audit committee independence and female leadership is expected to enhance sustainability reporting integrity.

Jibril et al. (2024) conducted a study on Audit Committee Attributes, Board of Directors' Independence and Energy Disclosure for Environmental Sustainability in Nigeria. The sample comprised 47 firms covering 2014–2020. A quantitative research design was employed, and panel data analysis was performed using STATA. The results revealed that audit committee independence significantly enhances environmental sustainability disclosure, particularly within energy-intensive sectors. The methodological approach allowed for robust statistical estimation of causal links between governance structures and disclosure outcomes. However, the study focused exclusively on energy disclosure, which limits its generalizability to broader sustainability themes. Hendrati and Prameswari (2023) also examined the moderating effect of audit committee and

board of directors on sustainability-report planning in Indonesia. A total of 122 respondents participated, covering 2021–2022. A survey-based quantitative design was adopted, and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was utilized. Findings indicated that audit committee independence positively moderates the relationship between the board’s sustainability orientation and reporting practices, suggesting that independent members strengthen governance oversight. The study was limited to self-reported survey data, which introduces potential bias in the findings.

Ubiomoh and Okoye (2024) investigated the Effect of Audit Committee Independence on Environmental Sustainability Disclosure in Nigeria. Using 50 firms from 2018–2022, the study employed an archival quantitative design and applied multiple regression analysis through SPSS. Results showed that firms with fully independent audit committees disclose significantly more environmental information than those with partially independent structures. The methodology’s use of secondary data improved the objectivity of analysis. Nevertheless, environmental reporting was examined without incorporating social or governance indicators, limiting the scope of interpretation. Similarly, Florea and Burcă (2024) analyzed Audit Committee Independence and Expertise at Company Level in Streamlining ESG Reporting in Romania. The research covered 62 firms for 2019–2022, adopting a cross-sectional empirical design and applying ordinary least squares (OLS) regression using RStudio. The results indicated that audit committee independence improves both the consistency and reliability of ESG reporting, with independent members providing more objective oversight of non-financial disclosures. The sample was limited to public companies rather than banks, which restricts the breadth of sectoral application.

Also, Buallay and Al-Ajmi (2020) assessed The Role of Audit Committee Attributes in Corporate Sustainability Reporting: Evidence from Banks in the GCC Countries. The study analyzed 76 banks from 2012–2018 using a panel-data research design and fixed-effects regression in EViews. Findings showed that audit committee independence is strongly associated with enhanced CSR and sustainability disclosures, implying that independent oversight promotes transparency and accountability. However, the study lacked an explicit theory it anchored on, which may affect the interpretive depth of its conclusions. Qaderi et al. (2023) further carried out a study on Audit Committee Leadership Attributes and CSR Reporting: Evidence from Jordan based on data from 63 publicly listed companies between 2016 and 2021. The study utilized a panel design and applied fixed-effects regression using EViews. The findings revealed that female-led audit committees exhibited a significantly greater demand for sustainability assurance and provided more detailed CSR disclosures than male-led committees. The study’s methodological framework enhanced its capacity to isolate leadership effects. However, it did not explore industry-specific variations, which could influence CSR assurance patterns.

Abu Alia et al. (2024) examined the question; Can Effective Boards Drive Environmental Innovation? They evaluated the Moderating Power of CSR Committees using 95 manufacturing firms in the MENA region from 2015–2021. Employing SEM design with AMOS, the findings indicated that audit committees chaired by women strengthened the influence of CSR committees in promoting environmental innovation. The integration of structural modeling improved causal interpretation and contributed to governance literature linking gender leadership to innovation outcomes. However, the study was limited by its reliance on innovation proxies such as patent applications, which may not fully capture all aspects of environmental performance.

Abu Khalaf (2024) conducted a study on Board Characteristics and the Adoption of Sustainable Reporting Practices using 89 Middle Eastern companies between 2014 and 2021. The research employed a panel design and regression analysis through SPSS. The findings showed that audit committees chaired by women ensured stricter supervision and timelier sustainability disclosures, reflecting improved monitoring discipline. The study's use of cross-sectoral data provided a broader contextual understanding of gender leadership. Nevertheless, it did not address cultural variables that may shape gender dynamics in corporate governance.

Behbahaninia and Bamshad (2025) investigated The Presence of Women in the Board and Audit Committee on Agency Costs using a sample of 78 firms listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange over 2016–2022. The study adopted a Generalized Least Squares (GLS) regression method within a panel framework using STATA. Results revealed that audit committees chaired by women significantly reduced agency costs and improved ESG disclosure transparency. The methodological rigor provided evidence of gendered leadership's impact on governance efficiency. However, the study did not incorporate comparative analysis across industries, which limits its general applicability. Furthermore, Abbasi et al. (2024) conducted a study on Female Director Expertise and Audit Committees Matter for Carbon Disclosures? Evidence from the United Kingdom using FTSE 350 firms over 2016–2021. The study employed a cross-sectional design and utilized both OLS and Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS) regression models in STATA to control for endogeneity. Findings indicated that female-led audit committees with accounting or financial expertise were associated with higher carbon disclosure quality. The dual-method estimation enhanced the robustness of the results. However, the research was confined to carbon disclosures and did not examine broader ESG indicators.

After reviewing prior empirical literature from various authors across different sectors concerning the variables employed in their studies, this study aim to address identified gaps such as the domain and regions which these studies were carried out by incorporating women chairpersons as a moderating variable. This will be examined alongside the effect of audit committee independence on sustainability reporting disclosure in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the ex-post facto (causal–comparative) research design. This design is considered appropriate because the variables of interest already exist and cannot be manipulated by the researcher. The study seeks to examine the effect of audit committee independence on sustainability reporting of listed deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria and the moderating role of the audit committee women chairperson. The ex-post facto design has been widely used in corporate governance and disclosure-related studies where data are obtained from secondary sources such as audited annual reports (Onuorah & Imene, 2022; Ubiomoh & Okoye, 2024).

The population of this study comprises fourteen (14) listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria as at 31st December, 2023. Given the relatively small size of the population, the study adopted a census sampling approach, where the 14 listed Deposit Money Banks were included in the sample over a fifteen (15) year span (2010-2024). This approach ensures that the results reflect the characteristics of the entire population of listed DMBs in Nigeria. Similar studies in the field of corporate governance and sustainability (e.g., Usman, 2024; Tumwebaze & Kaawaase, 2022) have adopted a full population sample where the number of listed entities was limited and publicly available data existed.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size of the Study

S/N	Bank Name	Year of Incorporation	Year of Listing
1.	Access Bank Plc	1989	1998
2.	Ecobank Nigeria Plc	1986	2006
3.	Fidelity Bank Plc	1988	1999
4.	FirstBank of Nigeria Plc	1894	1971
5.	First City Monument Bank	1982	2004
6.	Guarantee Trust Bank Plc	1990	2007
7.	Jaiz Bank plc	2003	2015
8.	Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc	1989	1989
9.	Sterling Bank Plc	1960	1992
10.	Union Bank Plc	1917	1971
11.	United Bank for Africa Plc	1961	1970
12.	Unity Bank Plc	170	1987
13.	Wema Bank Plc	1945	1973
14.	Zentih Bank Plc	1990	2004

This study adapted the model used by Ani et al (2020) as stated below;

$$SR = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{Size} + \beta_2\text{Liquid} + \beta_3\text{Profit} + \beta_4\text{Meet} + e \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$SR = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{Size} + \beta_2\text{Liquid} + \beta_3\text{Profit} + \beta_4\text{Meet} + \beta_5\text{Size*Meet} + \beta_6\text{Liquid*Meet} + \beta_7\text{Profit*Meet} + e \text{ ----- (2)}$$

Where;

SR is Sustainability Reporting

Size = Firm Size

Liquid = Liquidity

Profit = Profitability

Meet = Meeting

B_0 = intercept when the independent variables is zero

B_1 - β_7 = Regression Coefficient

i = Number of Firms

t = Period of the study

e = Error term

The independent variables (Size, Liquid and Profit) used in their study as well as the moderating variable (Meeting) were expunged and replaced with our own independent variable (Audit Committee Independence), control variable (Bank Size) and Women Chairpersons serving as a moderating variable. The modified regression equation of Model 1 and Model 2 in this study are therefore seen as follows:

Model 1

$$SDQI = \beta_0 + \beta_1ACIN_{it} + \beta_2ACWC_{it} + \beta_3BASZ_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Model 2

$$SDQI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACIN_{it} + \beta_2 ACWC_{it} + \beta_3 (ACIN * ACWC)_{it} + \beta_4 BASZ_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (4)}$$

Where;

SDQI = Sustainability Disclosure Quality Index (Dependent Variable)

ACIN = Audit Committee Independence (Independent Variable)

ACWC = Audit Committee Women Chairperson (Moderator Variable)

BASZ = Bank Size (Control Variable)

B₀ = intercept when the independent variables is zero

B₁- B₄ = Regression Coefficient

i = Number of Banks

t = Period of the study

e = Error term

Table 2: Variables, Definition, Measurement and Source

Variables	Definition	Measurement	Source(s)	Sign (+/-)
Sustainability Reporting Quality (SDQI)	Sustainability Reporting Quality refers to the degree of completeness, accuracy, and consistency in disclosing environmental, social, and governance (ESG) information.	Measured by coding scale of three thresholds: 0 = Sustainability reports do not exist. 1 = Sustainability reports exist. 2 = Presence of Sustainability reports & sustainability committee	Ani et al (2020)	Positive
Audit Committee Independence (ACIN)	Audit committee independence refers to the degree to which audit committee members are free from management influence and conflicts of interest.	Equals to 1 if the audit committee is independent, and 0 if otherwise	Beasley et al. (2000)	Positive
Audit Committee Women Chairperson (ACWC)	Audit Committee Women Chairperson represents the gender composition of leadership within the audit committee, specifically when the chairperson is a woman.	Presence of female director in the committee = 1, Absence = 0	Aifuwa & Embele (2019), Mustafa et al. (2018)	Positive
Bank Size (BASZ)	Bank Size reflects the scale of a bank's operations and financial strength, influencing its level of	Natural log of total assets	Chaudhry et al. (2020)	Positive

public visibility and
disclosure obligation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 present the descriptive statistics for the key variables used in this study; Audit Committee Independence (ACIN), Bank Size (BASZ), Sustainability Disclosure Quality Index (SDQI) and the moderating variable: Audit Committee Women Chairperson (ACWC). It provides an overview and offer insights into key statistical measures such as the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values for the variables used in this study.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SDQI	210	.2642857	.2209932	0	.75
ACIN	210	.5714286	.4960542	0	1
ACWC	210	.1095238	.3130415	0	1
BASZ	210	27.4821	1.530762	23.15179	31.39923

Source: Stata 13, 2025

Table 3 presented the descriptive statistics for the variables in the study which highlight notable variations in sustainability reporting practices in Nigerian deposit money banks. The SDQI (Sustainability Disclosure Quality Index) has a mean of 26.43% and a standard deviation of 22.1%, indicating moderate variability in sustainability reporting across banks ranging from a minimum of 0% to maximum of 75%. The ACIN (Audit Committee Independence) shows a mean of 5.7 with a standard deviation of 0.73, reflecting moderate variability, with committee independence ranging from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of 1. The BASZ (Bank Size) has a mean of 27.48, with a standard deviation of 1.53, indicating a significant variation in bank sizes, with a minimum of 23.15 and a maximum of 31.40. The ACWC (Audit Committee Women Chairperson) has a low mean of 0.11 with a standard deviation of 0.31, indicating moderate variation in gender diversity across banks, where some banks have no women chairing the committee (0), while others have (1). These descriptive statistics suggest varied approaches to sustainability reporting, with areas for improvement, particularly in gender diversity and consistency in reporting practice.

The correlation matrix reveals the degree of relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables as shown in Table 4

Table 4: Correlation matrix

VARIABLES	SDQI	ACIN	ACWC	BASZ
SDQI	1.0000			
ACIN	0.2634	1.0000		
ACWC	0.2366	0.0572	1.0000	
BASZ	0.2869	0.2473	0.3606	1.0000

Source: Stata 13, 2025

The correlation matrix in the table above reveals that there is a positive correlation between SDQI and ACIN at 0.2634, suggesting that an independent audit committee is generally associated with

higher sustainability reporting quality. Similarly, there is a strong positive correlation between SDQI and ACWC at 0.2366 indicating that the presence of women as chairpersons in the audit committee have a notable relationship with sustainability reporting quality in these sample of banks. Similarly, BASZ also has a strong positive correlation with SDQI, this implies that larger banks tend to have more extensive and better-quality sustainability disclosures, possibly due to their greater asset base.

The diagnostic test was were conducted in the study to improve the validity and reliability of the statistical results. These include Normality test, Multi-collinearity test, Heteroscedasticity test and Hausman specification test.

Normality Test

Table 5: Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	Z	Prob>z
SDQI	210	0.98568	2.229	1.849	0.03222
ACIN	210	0.99925	0.117	-4.944	1.00000
ACWC	210	0.93139	10.681	5.463	0.00000
BASZ	210	0.99265	1.144	0.311	0.37788

Source: Stata 13, 2025

The result on table 5 shows that the data for SDQI and ACWC does not follow normal distribution, this is due to the fact that the p-values of their Z-statistics are statistically significant at 0.03222 and 0.00000 respectively. The lack of normal distribution calls for robustness of regression technique. However, data set used for this study is normally distributed for BASZ at a p-value of 0.37788. For data set to be considered normal, the p-value have to be greater than 0.05 (Ghasemi & Zahediasl 2012).

Multicollinearity test

Table 6: Multicollinearity

Variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	VIF	1/VIF	VIF	1/VIF
BASZ	1.22	0.818383	1.24	0.807855
ACIN	1.06	0.937646	1.16	0.859835
ACWC	1.15	0.868859	2.86	0.349123
ACINACWC	-	-	3.01	0.332128
Mean VIF	1.15		2.07	

Source: Stata 13, 2025

The variance inflation factor (VIF) values were calculated for the independent variables for both model 1 and model 2 and the results shows that VIF value is below 5 and tolerance value is above 0.1, indicating no multicollinearity.

Heteroskedasticity test

Table 7: Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Model (SDQI)	Chi2 (1)	Prob > chi2
Model 1	2.13	0.1446
Model 2	2.24	0.1348

Source: Stata 13, 2025

The Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity was conducted for both model 1 and model 2 and the result was not significant (p-value > 0.05) for model 1 and model 2 indicating no presence of heteroscedasticity in the data.

Hausman Specification test

The hausman specification test was conducted in order to determine whether the fixed effect model or the random effect model is most appropriate for the study and the difference in coefficient was insignificant (Prob > chi2=0.6379) as shown in Table 8. This indicate that the random effect model is most appropriate.

Table 8: Hausman Specification test

Chi ² (4)	Prob > chi ²
2.54	0.6379

Source: Stata 13, 2025

Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test

The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects was carried out to determine whether to use random effect model or a pooled OLS model. The result in Table 9 showed that the p-value is significant at 0.0000 indicating that the random effect model should be used.

Table 9: Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test

Chibar ² (01)	Prob > chibar ²
343.68	0.0000

Source: Stata 13, 2025

Regression Result

Table 10: Regression Result

Variables	Model 1 (Pooled OLS)			Model 2 (Random Effect)		
	Coef.	t	p>t	Coef.	t	p>t
SDQI						
ACIN	.0937791	3.16	0.002	.0300297	3.03	0.002
ACWC	.11354	2.33	0.021	.0274609	2.4	0.016
BASZ	.0255242	2.48	0.014	.0398441	5.44	0.000
ACINACWC	-	-	-	-.2563999	-1.4	0.163
_cons	-.5031953	-1.81	0.007	-2.121893	-3.50	0.001
			1			
F-Statistics (Prob)	11.57(0.0000)			53.82(0.0000)		
R²	0.1442			0.2183		

Adjusted R²	0.1318	0.1376
-------------------------------	---------------	---------------

Source: Stata 132025

Model 1 evaluates the effect of audit committee independence on the sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria, as shown in Table 10. The regression results reveal an R² value of 0.1442, signifying that approximately 14.42% of the variation in sustainability reporting is explained by the independent variables in the model. The adjusted R² of 0.1318 further indicates that about 13.18% of the variation is accounted for after controlling for model complexity. Additionally, the Prob (F-statistic) of 0.0000 confirms that the model is statistically significant at the 1% level.

The coefficient of 0.0937791, corresponding to a t-value of 3.16 and a p-value of 0.002, demonstrates that audit committee independence exerts a positive and statistically significant effect on sustainability reporting among Nigerian deposit money banks. This finding implies that variations in audit committee independence meaningfully influence the extent of sustainability disclosures. Consequently, the null hypothesis stating that audit committee independence has no significant effect on sustainability reporting is rejected. This result corroborates the findings of Jibril et al. (2024), Ubiomoh and Okoye (2024), and Florea and Burrecă (2024), who similarly reported a significant association between audit committee independence and sustainability reporting quality.

Likewise, the coefficient of 0.11354, with a t-value of 2.33 and p-value of 0.021, indicates that the audit committee women chairperson variable has a positive and statistically significant effect on sustainability reporting. Therefore, the null hypothesis suggesting that the audit committee women chairperson has no significant effect on sustainability reporting is also rejected. This finding aligns with prior studies conducted by Zampone et al. (2024), Almonte (2025), and Qaderi et al. (2023), which found that female leadership within audit committees enhances sustainability disclosure practices. However, it diverges from the earlier work of Nishii and Mayer (2009), which revealed that gender of the audit committee chairperson alone did not have a direct influence on sustainability reporting improvement.

Model 2 explores the moderating influence of the audit committee women chairperson on the relationship between audit committee independence and sustainability reporting among Nigerian deposit money banks. The random effects regression output shows that the R² value is 0.2183, implying that approximately 21.83% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the predictors in the model. The adjusted R² of 0.1376 suggests that roughly 13.76% of the variance remains explained after accounting for model complexity. The Prob (F-statistic) of 0.0000 further confirms the overall statistical significance of the model at the 1% level.

However, the moderating variable, represented by the interaction term ACINACWC, yields a coefficient of -0.2563999 , a t-value of -1.4 , and a p-value of 0.163, which indicates an insignificant moderating effect. Accordingly, the null hypothesis asserting that the audit committee women chairperson does not significantly moderate the relationship between audit committee independence and sustainability reporting cannot be rejected. This finding suggests that the moderating role of female leadership on audit committees does not significantly influence sustainability disclosure levels among listed Nigerian banks.

Although substantial evidence exists supporting the beneficial impact of women chairpersons on improving sustainability reporting (Zampone et al., 2024; Almonte, 2025; Qaderi et al., 2023), the

moderating effect in this study appears statistically weak. This could be attributed to contextual factors such as organizational culture, regulatory environments, or sectoral norms that may dilute the moderating influence of female leadership within audit committees. Future studies should therefore consider examining the situational and institutional dynamics that may enhance or constrain the effectiveness of women leadership roles in audit committees in promoting sustainability disclosure.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The primary objective of this study was to assess the impact of audit committee independence on sustainability reporting and to examine the moderating influence of the audit committee women chairperson among listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria between 2010 and 2024. The study concludes that audit committee independence exerts a significant positive influence on the sustainability reporting practices of Nigerian listed DMBs. In a similar vein, the findings showed that the presence of a female chairperson in the audit committee also significantly enhances sustainability reporting. However, the study further revealed that the audit committee women chairperson does not significantly moderate the relationship between audit committee independence and sustainability reporting in the Nigerian banking sector.

Based on the conclusions from this study, it is recommended that listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria should strengthen the independence of their audit committees by ensuring that a greater proportion of members are non-executive and independent directors with diverse expertise. Such independence enhances objective oversight and improves the transparency of sustainability disclosures. Furthermore, banks should continue to promote gender diversity by encouraging and appointing more qualified women to chair audit committees, as this has been shown to positively influence sustainability reporting practices. However, since the moderating role of female chairpersons was found to be statistically insignificant, regulatory authorities such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) should develop policies that go beyond mere representation and focus on empowering female leaders through targeted capacity-building programs, sustainability training, and inclusion in strategic decision-making processes. This could help translate gender representation into more effective governance outcomes and improved sustainability performance among banks in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Abbasi, M., Khan, R., & Malik, S. (2024). Does female director expertise on audit committees matter for carbon disclosures? Evidence from the United Kingdom. *Journal of Corporate Governance*, 19(3), 122–138.
- Ademola, O., Akintoye, R., & Ogunleye, F. (2022). Audit qualities and sustainability reports of oil and gas companies listed on the NSE. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(4), 201–215.
- Adewuyi, A. O., & Abiola, R. O. (2022). Audit committee attributes and sustainability reporting in emerging economies. *Sustainability Accounting Review*, 14(2), 45–61.

- Alalade, Y. S. A., & Ogboi, C. (2024). ESG reporting and financial performance of deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Seybold Report.
- Amin, K., Yamaguchi, T., & Sato, N. (2021). Audit committee characteristics and corporate biodiversity disclosure: Evidence from Japan. *Asian Journal of Accounting and Governance*, 15(2), 44–59.
- Aprianti, A., Kusuma, H., & Hartono, R. (2021). Audit committee and sustainability report: Evidence from Indonesia. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Finance*, 7(2), 100–115.
- Ben Amar, A., Ben Salah, F., & Othman, H. (2024). Corporate environmental disclosure and earnings management: The moderating effect of female board representation. *Journal of Sustainable Accounting*, 12(1), 33–51.
- Buallay, A., & Al-Ajmi, J. (2020). The role of audit committee attributes in corporate sustainability reporting: Evidence from the GCC countries. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 21(2), 249–272.
- Eccles, R. G., & Krzus, M. P. (2018). *The integrated reporting movement: Meaning, momentum, motives, and materiality*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26(2), 301–325. <https://doi.org/10.1086/467037>
- Florea, C., & Burcă, R. (2024). Impact of audit committee independence and expertise on ESG reporting: Evidence from Romania. *European Journal of Financial Studies*, 11(2), 75–94.
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic management: A stakeholder approach*. Pitman.
- Gatimbu, K., & Kariuki, S. (2025). Audit committee diversity and sustainability in Sub-Saharan Africa. *African Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 18(1), 89–108.
- Gupta, P., & Sharma, A. (2020). Corporate governance and sustainability reporting: A study of Indian firms. *Journal of Business Ethics and Sustainability*, 9(2), 45–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbes.2020.02.004>
- Hendrati, D., & Prameswari, R. (2023). Moderating activities of the audit committee and board of directors on sustainability reporting in Indonesia. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Studies*, 10(4), 32–49.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360.
- Jibril, A., Okonkwo, I., & Aliyu, M. (2024). Audit committee attributes, board independence, and energy disclosure for environmental sustainability in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 15(1), 41–58.

- Jibril, M. A., Okoye, P. V., & Bello, S. (2024). Audit committee attributes, board independence, and energy disclosure for environmental sustainability in Nigeria. *African Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 19(1), 101–118.
- Karim, M., & Dhar, S. (2024). Audit committee characteristics and sustainable firm performance: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Journal of Corporate Governance Studies*, 7(1), 66–83.
- Kolk, A. (2004). A decade of sustainability reporting: Developments and significance. *International Journal of Environment and Sustainable Development*, 3(1), 51-64. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJESD.2004.004922>
- Lozano, R. (2021). Sustainability reporting and performance: Corporate responsibility beyond compliance. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(2), 705–720.
- Onuorah, A. C., & Imene, C. C. (2022). Corporate governance mechanisms and sustainability performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 8(3), 44–60.
- Oyerogba, E. O., & Oladele, F. (2024). Corporate governance practices and sustainability reporting quality: Evidence from Nigerian listed financial institutions. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 2325111.
- Pfeffer, J., & Salancik, G. R. (1978). *The external control of organizations: A resource dependence perspective*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Soyemi, K. A., Adebayo, S. A., & Fatai, G. A. (2024). Nexus between board characteristics and firm performance of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting & Finance*, 10(10), 174-202.
- Terjesen, S., Sealy, R., & Singh, V. (2009). Women directors on corporate boards: A review and research agenda. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 17(3), 320–337. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2009.00742>.
- Tumwebaze, Z., & Kaawaase, T. (2022). Audit committee effectiveness, internal audit function, and sustainability reporting practices in Uganda. *African Journal of Governance*, 14(2), 199–217.
- Ubiomoh, O., & Okoye, P. V. (2024). Audit committee independence and environmental sustainability disclosure in Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Reporting*, 12(1), 88–104.
- Usman, H. (2024). Board attributes and sustainability reporting quality: Moderating role of audit quality in Nigeria. *Journal of Corporate Reporting*, 9(1), 67–85.

Waseem, A., Khan, U., & Raza, M. (2024). Impact of audit committee attributes and liquidity on sustainability reporting in Pakistan. *Asian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 17(4), 144–160.